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CORRIGENDUM

Corrigendum to: A Cross-sectional Serological Study for Measles among Italian Medical Students in 2020

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We would like to apologize for an error that occurred in the online version of the article. The principal author's name was published incorrect in the article entitled "A Cross-sectional Serological Study for Measles among Italian Medical Students in 2020" in "The Open Public Health Journal", 2020 Dec 23;13(1) [1].

The original article can be found online at <https://openpublichealthjournal.com/VOLUME/13/PAGE/692/>

Original:

The name of coauthor was Trabucco Aurilio Marco

Corrected:

The name of coauthor has been revised as M. Trabucco Aurilio

REFERENCE

- [1] Marco TA, Iannuzzi I, Di Giampaolo L, Pietroiusti A, Ferrari C, Coppeta L. A Cross-sectional Serological Study for Measles among Italian Medical Students in 2020. *Open Public Health J* 2020; 13(1) [<http://dx.doi.org/10.2174/1874944502013010692>]

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